

Examine the mediating role of environmental concern and perceived benefit on adoption of Green Accounting with the Emerging Economy Perspective

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Abstract:

This study investigates into influence of environmental knowledge, environmental concern and perceived benefit on Green Accounting adoption in micro, small, and medium enterprise. This study was consider because of insufficient availability of literature regarding the adoption of green accounting in emerging economies. The entire cross sectional study was conducted with 431 responses of business leader from various part of Gujarat. The study revealed the positive impact of environmental knowledge, environmental concern and perceived benefit on Green Accounting adoption. Moreover, this study exhibit the mediating role of Environmental Concern and Perceived Benefit, like higher knowledge of environment leads to environmental concern and subsequently resulted in enhancing adoption of Green Accounting. The findings of this study provides valuable insights to marketers, policy makers of green accounting products, environmental policy makers, and business leader. It helps managers and policy makers to design and formulate strategies related to green accounting in emerging economies.

Key Words: Green Accounting, Environmental Knowledge, Environmental Concern, Perceived Benefit, MSME, Emerging Economies

Introduction

There was a recent pandemic that emphasized the importance of nature. Decision makers show concern for environmental factors while making decisions. The majority of entrepreneurs incline to apply environmental resources to reduce the cost and showing concern regarding the environment. The current trend indicator that many organizations apply a green accounting system in their routine day to day operations (Wan, Y. K., Ng, R. T., Ng, D. K., & Tan, R. R., 2015). The most of manufacturing companies like Pharma, textiles, Engineering, chemicals and service sector organizations like information technology, hospitals, hospitality, Financial Services, education have adopted green accounting. Recent European reports suggest that the Global Green Technology market size was valued at 10. 32 billion dollars in 2020, (Eurobarometer, S, 2009)it is estimated to reach 74.64 billion dollars 22% approximately in 2030 (Hower, M. , 2013). The reason for the increasing effect of green accounting is that entrepreneurs understand the importance of the concept of sustainability, societal responsibility and most vital is the cost effectiveness (Biswas, A., & Roy, M. , 2015). Central and state governments are also putting lots of effort into creating awareness, providing financial assistance and benefits. All corporate strategic decision makers are aware of the fact that the financial sector plays a very crucial role in utilizations of resources, Mobilization of various instruments, routine transactions and manufacturing

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resources (Wymer, W., & Polonsky, M. J., 2015). Green in emerging markets like India, green accounting focuses on sustainability, cost effectiveness, appropriate usages of resources and most importantly effectiveness of existing employees can be traced (Nasreen, S., Anwar, S., & Ozturk, I., 2017). In addition to that it addresses dynamic interrelations amongst the various drivers of economic growth in developing countries (Tucker, E. M., Rifon, N. J., Lee, E. M., & Reece, B. B. , 2012).

The most important aspects of green accounting can be adapted by manufacturing and service Sector organizations. Even small and medium size organizations applied these tools without any hassle. With the advancement of technological age and the unprecedented growth of industries, any organization faces lots of challenges with respect to satisfying the needs of customers, facing the challenges of competitors and most importantly always remains ahead of Rivals (Vora, H., Jadhav, D., & Bhatt, V., 2020) (Bhatt, V. , 2021). To survive in the complex competitive era, adoption of Technology is the only solution (Rosenbaum, M. S., & Wong, I. A. , 2015). Most of the growing organizations Decided to adapt green accounting to satisfy the need of customer preferences and survive in the technological environment. Gradually Industrialist became more aware regarding social and environmental Concern about production and operation and its financial implication.

Green accounting comprises the power of accounting systems to identify records, reports of environmental, Degradation of pollution (El Serafy, S., 1997). The core purpose of environmental accounting is to help managers to evaluate existing performance and to take appropriate decisions. Recently top managers intended to provide services even after selling products, hence current organization issues not only related to making profit but they also focus on Customer Management, customer satisfaction and social economic responsibility (Farouk, S., Cherian, J., & Jacob, J. , 2012) . These companies will take interest to use Green accounting as a strategic management tools and simultaneously they want to give a delighted feeling to their customers (PaPalmer, M., & Truong, Y., 2017). Most of the companies adopt environmental accounting to increase efficiency, managing operational effective cost and generate satisfaction amongst the various stakeholders (Stanojević, M., Vraneš, S., & Gökalp, I., 2010). The core purpose of environmental accounting is to contribute something to society and nation building (Suki, N. M., 2013).

The most crucial aspects of this study is to understand the positive contribution of various predictors and examine the effects of each of the exogenous variables on Green accounting adoption (Bhatt, V. , 2021). To address the differentiation amongst various existing contributions and our proposed contribution, this study examines the role of Environment knowledge (ENK), Environmental concern (ENC) and the most important factor is perceived benefit (PB) on adoption of Green accounting (Carrete, L., Castaño, R., Felix, R., Centeno, E., & González, E., 2012). Majority of previous studies contribution apply the longitudinal studies. Previous studies focused more on financial performance and how different financial indicators affect the profitability of certain organizations or specific sectors, or contribution in the economy. This is the very unique cross section effort. This study aims to examine the impact of ENK, ENC and PB on adoption of Green accounting in any manufacturing or service organization in GUJARAT. In addition to that in this research ENC and PB mediating impact is evaluated on adoption of green accounting in micro, small, medium enterprises in one of the fastest growing state of country (Raska, D., & Shaw, D. , 2012).

While selection of geographic region, Gujarat is considered as land of entrepreneur and one of rapid progressive state of INDIA. Moreover ASIA's two largest industrial areas are part of Gujarat state. There are more than fifty versatile industrial areas that are working very efficiently and more than three lacs SMEs are functioning progressively. This is the state promoted as a model industrial developing state of the country, therefore GUJARAT state is our obvious choice as the geographic region of our research.

While addressing the third research gap, previous study contributes with historical accounting analysis and majority of them applied ratio and trend analysis. This is a very novel approach of creating models with predictors like ENK, ENC AND PB measuring their impact on adoption of green accounting. This study is an attempt to understand the opinion of business leaders regarding adoption of green accounting concepts in their organizations. This study not only focuses on the direct effect of predictors but also addresses the mediating role of valuable contributors like ENC and PB on adoption or intent to purchase green accounting in a changing business environment.

AT the outset, the above discussion will address the following questions.

- (1) What positive factors influence the business leaders to take decisions related to green accounting?
- (2) What is the direct role of factors like environmental knowledge, environmental concern and perceived benefit of influencing business leaders to adopt green accounting?
- (3) What are the mediating effects of environmental concern and perceived benefits between environmental knowledge and green accounting adoption?

LITERATURE REVIEW:

To address aforementioned research questions, researchers conduct extensive literature in the area of green accounting. The study emphasizes the role of environmental knowledge, environmental concern and perceived benefit, while making the adoption of green accounting in MSMES in developing economies. The green accounting concepts, usually contextual variables, influence any individual's potential to perform. This is the modern tools uses existing and new source natural tools will create demand of natural and green products gradually will strengthen economy of developing countries. This is unconventional easy clear process; mainly rely on natural resources and creating sustainability of economic performance. Knowledge of environment explores how to manage natural resources. In the existing complex business system, this is very vital task to understand the natural resources protection and create environmental management system that is linked with our business management system.

Environmental Knowledge:

Term environmental knowledge means basic ideas, facts, various points of view and relationship with other aspects (Fryxell, G. E., & Lo, C. W., 2003). It indicates that an entrepreneur is aware of issues, challenges showing personal concern and most important aspects is emotional touch with other human beings (Do Paco, A., & Raposo, M., 2009) (Zhao, H. H., Gao, Q., Wu, Y. P., Wang, Y., & Zhu, X. D., 2014) . Our study focuses on the role of environmental knowledge in the adoption of green accounting. (Bamberg, S., & Möser, G, 2007) Suggested that environmental knowledge plays a very crucial role in

building consumer attitude and adoption of environmental products. Environmental knowledge motivates customers to influence pro green product behaviors (D'Souza, C., Taghian, M., & Khosla, R., 2007) .

Environmental knowledge plays a very vital role in decision makers' attitude, behaviors when division related to the environment's human concern and it gives benefit to organization as well as mankind [(Chang, M. C., & Wu, C. C. , 2015), (Suki, N. M., 2013)].

The above mentioned study indicates that environmental knowledge influences consumers' to adopt environment friendly products and intent to purchase the products.

H1: Environmental knowledge will have a positive impact on green accounting adoption.

H2 : Environmental knowledge will have a positive impact on perceived benefit.

H3 : Environmental knowledge will have a positive impact on environmental concern.

Perceived Benefit:

This is the most crucial factor of the study; perceived benefit plays a very vital role in adoption of green accounting. Perceived benefit consists of five different aspects. The first aspect is social value, economical value, psychological value, emotional value and most important realizations.(sheth.et.al, 1991). Economical and self-realizations motivate any individual to adopt green accounting (Ajmera, H., & Bhatt, V., 2020). Government initiatives like financial benefits, financial loan at subsidized rate,, various tax benefits, loan assistance from public sector banks inspire b business leaders to implement an environmentally friendly system. (Daus. 2002) The cost in any industry plays a very vital role, green accounting deals with operations and effectiveness of entire organizations financially. The cost effectiveness in any organization will help to earn more and gain additional; money for the stakeholders. Perceived benefits such as accumulated additional profit will lead to adoption of green accounting (Bhatt, V., 2021). Social value derives through the interactions amongst the various groups who adopt the green accounting process. These interactions amongst the society will provide additional gauge, social substance and most importantly such entrepreneurs can catch the attractions of the society (Joshi, D., & Bhatt, V., 2018). Green accounting holders are known for technological thinkers, environmental concern and contribution in nation building activities (Bernal, G., Bonilla, J., & Bellido, C. , 1995). These decisions not only affect the members of the organizations but it provides the sense of responsibility. The adoption of green accounting can be related with entrepreneur potential, individual achievements and a sense of gaining something important with individual abilities and skills. The empirical; evidences also received by various contributors in the past, higher the benefits will lead to adoption of technological products or services (Raval, H. P., & Bhatt, V., 2021). Consumers will get more benefit this will motivate them to adopt or purchase the product (Nagvadia, M. J., & Bhatt, V. , 2021). Hence, from the above discussions entrepreneurs or business leaders have various dimensions of adopting green accounting. Here we propose our hypothesis.

H4 : Perceived benefit will have positive impact on adoption of green accounting

Environmental concern:

In this study we consider environmental concern is an additional effort of an individual to protect the environment or involve in any specific challenge related to saving the

environment (Dunlap, R. E., & Van Liere, K. D., 1978) . Previous contributions of researcher suggest environmental concerns leads with an individual attitude, behavior, or their proactive intent to adopt environment friendly products (Kim, Y., & Choi, S. M. , 2005). In a similar direction (Mostafa, M. M. , 2006) suggested that environmental concern motivates individuals to purchase green products. Those business persons have positive beliefs, mindsets, and always think about organizations, society, stakeholders of the company and most importantly their duty towards the nation. Positive attitude towards the business leads him to purchase green products (Bang, H. K., Ellinger, A. E., Hadjimarcou, J., & Traichal, P. A., 2000). With higher levels of environmental concern found to be very positive regarding adoption of green accounting (Newton, J. D., Tsarenko, Y., Ferraro, C., & Sands, S., 2015). These customers of green products are very active, research oriented, define the problems in an articulate manner and ready to adopt new technology are ready to apply green initiatives. The above discussion shows that those persons with environmental concerns are positive, open minded and influential towards the adoption of green products. Here we propose the hypothesis that

H5 : Environmental concern will have a positive impact on adoption of green accounting.

Mediating effects:

In this study researchers propose mediating the effect of environmental concern and perceived benefit of green accounting. (Bamberg, S., & Möser, G, 2007) Derives that highly environmental knowledge oriented people are likely to be associated with green products or organic products or renewable energy. Past study found that customers with higher levels of environmental concerns were better informed regarding green technology and conscious about green products. Environmental concerns exhibit values, ethics and morals that lead to significant impact towards the green technology products (Kalafatis, S. P., Pollard, M., East, R., & Tsogas, M. H. , 1999). The empirical evidence found for mediating the role of environmental concerns. Past researchers evaluate that environmental concern influences the attitude of business persons to adopt green technological products. These people have strong beliefs, values regarding societal issues and showing concern to others. Hence, here we strongly propose the mediating role of environmental concern.

H6: Environmental concern mediates the relationship between Environmental Knowledge and adoption of green accounting.

This study also proposes the mediating role of perceived benefits. In the business emotional value, feelings, attitudes, directly affected to business activities. The cost effectiveness, financial benefit and commercial profit plays an important role to take any business decision (Nayak, K. M., Bhatt, V., & Nagvadia, J., 2021). The obvious choice for any business leaders is to higher the profit with social substance and fulfill the responsibility towards the stakeholder is preferred decisions. This will lead to image building, business identity and give additional tag of successful business organizations. The adoption of green accounting will help any business person to achieve five dimensions of the benefits and they are: 1. Social Motive, 2. Economical Motive, 3. Self Realization Motive, 4. Psychological Motive, and 5. Emotional Motive, easily. Environment knowledge inspires any business person to adopt green technological products. Hence, exhaustive benefits motivate business leaders to adopt green accounting concepts. Therefore, we recommend the mediating role of perceived benefit

to adopt green accounting in emerging economies (Tucker, E. M., Rifon, N. J., Lee, E. M., & Reece, B. B. , 2012). Thus we proposed that :

H7: Perceived Benefits mediate the relationship between Environmental knowledge and adoption of green accounting.

Research process

To address the above formulated hypothesis, this study concentrated on business owner of micro small medium Enterprise firms. This honor has either manufacturing unit or they owned service organizations. This business venture list are progressive, positive thinker, ready to adopt new technologies and most importantly there locations of organizations lies in Gujarat one of the growing state. In this study researcher apply non probability purposive sampling design (Malhotra, N., Nunan, D., & Birks, D., 2017). In the pre testing process, structured questionnaire reviewed by three senior academicians to ensure challenge is related to lay out, structure, appropriate order of the treatment and most importantly content and face validity. Pilot testing was conducted from 48 respondents from Ahmedabad and their responses were not considered in the final data set. The pilot data Analysis reveal that all pre identified variables Cronbach Alpha value greater than 0.70 (Chou, C. P., & Bentler, P. M. , 1995) ensure the reliability for all constructs.

The final survey was carried out in major industrial cities of GUJRAT Like Ahmedabad, Rajkot, Vadodara, Surat, Ankleshwar, Vapi, Jamnagar, Kadi , Gandhidham and Anand etc. The survey was conducted 4 month and 12 days in the year 2021. Average response time of a structured questionnaire was 21 minutes. There were 428 responses from business leaders collected from various cities. The final dataset was prepared with 405 complete questionnaires. The final data set was sufficient enough to perform variance based structural equation modeling (Myers, N. D., Ahn, S., & Jin, Y., 2011). This final data set is twenty one time more than (1:20) numbers of statements considered in the final structure questionnaire is much higher than the threshold of 10 times (Hair, J., Hollingsworth, C. L., Randolph, A. B., & Chong, A. Y. L., 2017). The data collection was conducted through personal interview method. The respondent opinion collected at their own place and they were briefed regarding the study, in addition to that they were educated related scaling techniques, there is no right or wrong answer of the statements.

Sector	MANUFACTURING	SERVICES	-	-	Total
	256	175	-	-	431
AGE	18-30	31-45	46>		
	186	149	96	-	431
EDUCATION	SCHOOL	GRADUATE	POST-GRADUATE	PROFESSIONALS	
	89	156	106	80	431
TURNOVER	<2	2-5	5-10	>10	
	82	157	106	86	431

Respondent characteristics Shows that, 40.6% (175) respondents were from service sectors, while 59.4% (256) from manufacturing sectors. Participants were from different age groups 18-30 (186,43.20%), 31-45 were(149, 34.60%), and 45 and above age group respondent were (96,22.30%).education and qualifications of business leader is important aspects, where 89 (20.6%) respondents were undergraduates, graduate respondent were 156(36.2%) outnumbered the post graduate students 106(24.6%) and professional were 80 (18.6%) respondents. The most crucial aspects of participants profile was turnover of the organizations, there were 82 (19%) respondents turnover less than 5cr , while 5-10 cr turnover of their unit were 157 (36.4%) , 10-20 cr turnover 106 (24.6%) and more than 20 cr turnover were 86 (20%) respondents.

The structural model consists of four variables: environmental knowledge, environmental concern, perceived benefits and green accounting adoption. The opinion of participants was collected by using a seven point Likert scale, where strongly disagree(1), disagree(2), somewhat disagree(3), neither agree nor disagree(4), somewhat agree(5), agree(6) and strongly agree coded with (7).. The structure questionnaire consist environmental knowledge predictor (4 items), two mediating variables environmental concern (6 items), perceived benefit (6 items) and endogenous variable of structure is green accounting adoption (5 items)., the item of green accounting adoption was removed because of low factor loadings (FL5=0.625<.0.70) (Hair, J., Hollingsworth, C. L., Randolph, A. B., & Chong, A. Y. L., 2017).

MULTIVARIATE ASSUMPTION:

Figure: Q – Q Plots.

Test of Normality:

Table 2: Tests of Normality						
	Kolmogorov-Smirnov ^a			Shapiro-Wilk		
	Statistic	Df	Sig.	Statistic	df	Sig.
OEKW	.167	431	.000	.905	431	.000
OPB	.105	431	.000	.942	431	.000
OGAD	.127	431	.000	.941	431	.000
OENC	.103	431	.000	.945	431	.000
a. Lilliefors Significance Correction						

Table 3: Test of Homogeneity of Variance:

Table 3: Test of Homogeneity of Variances					
		Levene Statistic	df1	df2	Sig.
OGAD	Based on Mean	.324	3	427	.808
	Based on Median	.337	3	427	.799
	Based on Median and with adjusted df	.337	3	425.598	.799
	Based on trimmed mean	.312	3	427	.816

Table 4: Linearity of relationships:

Table 4: ANOVA						
		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
OEKW	Between Groups	12.997	3	4.332	1.656	.176
	Within Groups	1117.054	427	2.616		
	Total	1130.052	430			
OPB	Between Groups	16.201	3	5.400	2.209	.086
	Within Groups	1043.930	427	2.445		
	Total	1060.131	430			
OENC	Between Groups	6.337	3	2.112	2.255	.081
	Within Groups	399.990	427	.937		
	Total	406.328	430			
Note: N=431, OEKW = Overall Environmental Knowledge, OPB = Overall Perceived Benefits, OENC = Overall Environmental Concern						

While performing multivariate analysis, study requires to verify some prior assumptions. Normality of data was evaluated by Shapiro wilk's test and QQ plots were performed. (Table : 2- and figure -1). The analysis revealed that the significance value of all pre-identified constructs was (0.00) which is less than (0.05) and graphical presentation of Q and Q plots (some of the points are not linear) clearly ensure the non-Normality of distribution. Homogeneity variance was tested by levene's test, significance value for Green accounting adoption was (sig=0. .808, Table :3), indicate that variability in the endogenous variables are equal. Linearity was performed with the linearity test, data analysis (Table: 4) shows all significance values for the test are above >0.05 ensure the linearity of this data set. Multicollinearity was tested through VIF (variance inflation factor), all the 20 statement VIF values are less than threshold 5 suggested by (Hew, T. S., & Kadir, S. L. S. A., 2016) confirm non-existence of multicollinearity (Table 5, C3) . In present data. To test the influence outlier cook's distance was performed with SPSS -26 version (Cook, R. D., 1977) influence statistics result suggest highest cook's distance value is 0.34 which is below benchmark suggested <0.50 ., ensure non-presence of influence outlier in present data set.

For the validation of model stone-geisser Q squared performed for each endogenous variables in the model (Kock, N., & Lynn, G. S., 2012), (Hair, J. F., Black, W. C., Babin, B. J., & Anderson, R. E., 2009)) with blindfolding , non-parametric value for all endogenous variables were perceived benefit (0.732) , environmental concern (.583) and adoption of green accounting was (0.657) which is higher than acceptable predictive validity suggested by (Kock, N., & Lynn, G. S., 2012)ensure the sufficient predictive validity of all three endogenous variables. To verify weather common method variance exist in this study or not, block variance inflation factor were calculated for all three predictors. For each block three predictor points at an endogenous variable. The inner variance inflation factor for each block is lower than 3.3 (Kock, N., & Lynn, G. S., 2012). The above results confirm non-existence of no vertical co linearity in a block. This results ensure or absence of common method variance in this study.

Table 5: Construct Reliability and Convergent Validity						
Indicator	FL	VIF	AVE	alpha	rho	CR
EKW1	0.93	4.19				
EKW2	0.91	3.60				
EKW3	0.91	3.65				
EKW4	0.93	4.16	0.85	0.90	0.92	0.95
PB1	0.91	4.00				
PB2	0.91	4.40				
PB3	0.90	3.96				
PB4	0.91	4.09				
PB5	0.89	3.59				
PB6	0.92	4.53	0.82	0.95	0.95	0.96
GAD1	0.88	2.67				
GAD2	0.87	2.60				

GAD3	0.87	2.41				
GAD4	0.90	2.95	0.77	0.90	0.91	0.93
ENC1	0.82	2.18				
ENC2	0.80	2.02				
ENC3	0.82	2.29				
ENC4	0.80	2.05				
ENC5	0.83	2.26				
ENC6	0.81	2.17	0.67	0.89	0.90	0.92

Statistical results discussion:

Inner model:

The measurement model was analyzed using PLS 3 software. Variance based SEM is the most suitable, robust technique to propose a new model which has not been statistically validated (Hair, J., Hollingsworth, C. L., Randolph, A. B., & Chong, A. Y. L., 2017). This study emphasized dual approach of evaluating inner and outer model (Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., and Sarstedt, M., 2016). Internal consistency of data evaluated through alpha and rho. The value of all latent constructs is greater than 0.70, ensuring reliability of data. The convergent validity evaluated by factor loadings, average variance extracted and composite reliability shows that factor loadings >0.70, AVE >0.50 and CR >0.70 are as per recommendations of (Hair et.al, 2017).

In addition to that for all pre-identified constructs, CR > AVE ensures convergent validity for inner models (Hair et.al, 2016). To test how all latent constructs are different from one another. In this study, discriminant validity was applied. Foreigner and lacker and HTMT (Heterotrait-Monotrait) was performed. Indicate that the square root of AVE is higher than intra-construct calculation (Lowery and Gaskin 2014). In addition to that, all HTMT values are less than its threshold values of 0.85 (Ab Hamid, M. R., Sami, W., & Sidek, M. M., 2017). Considering the results of above analysis, discriminant validity is established in the study.

Table 6: Fornell-Larcker's criterion, Inter-Construct Correlations (IC), and Heterotrait-Monotrait (HTMT) Ratio for discriminant validity

Table 6: Discriminant Validity				
Construct	GAD	EKW	PB	ENC
GAD	{0.7772}			
EKW	[0.2855] (0.5774)	{0.8488}		
PB	[0.2476] (0.5332)	[0.4233] (0.6843)	{0.8174}	
ENC	[0.1721]	[0.0685]	[0.1055]	{0.6640}

(0.4573) (0.2813) (0.3494)

Bold values on the diagonal within curly brackets {} indicate Square roots of AVEs. The scores in the lower diagonal within square brackets [] indicate inter-construct correlations, IC, values within round brackets () indicate Hetero-Trait-Mono-Trait (HTMT) Ratio

Structural model:

To examine and analyze the structural model of study SMARTPLS 3 was performed with 5000 bootstrapping resample with similar sign (Hair, J. F., Hult, G. T. M., Ringle, C., and Sarstedt, M., 2016). This technique is a widely applied, proven method of comparing the original results with resampled performance. The path analysis results indicate that environmental knowledge has a positive impact on green accounting adoption with ($\beta = 0.3240$, $t = 6.77$, $\text{sig} = 0.000$). If any business person improve environmental knowledge by 10% than 3.2 chances for incremental green accounting adoption. In addition to that environmental knowledge has a positive influence on two mediating variables that is environmental concern and perceived benefits.

Table 7: Bootstrapping and effect size

Effect	β	t	Significance	Decision	F ²	Decision
EKW → GAD	0.342	6.77	0.00	Support	0.1094	Medium
EKW → PB	0.650	25.06	0.00	Support	0.7340	Strong
EKW → ENC	0.2617	5.82	0.00	Support	0.080	Medium
PB →GAD	0.19	3.75	0.002	Support	0.04	Low
ENC → GAD	0.2638	5.75	0.00	Support	0.100	Medium

Data analysis table shows that environmental knowledge to environmental concern is ($\beta = 0.2617$, $t = 5.82$, $\text{sig} = 0.00$) and environmental knowledge have positive impact on perceived benefit ($\beta = 0.65606$, $t = 25.06$, $\text{sig} = 0.00$) This is strongest relationship of structural model which supports H3 and H4. Moreover in this study evaluate two additional direct relationships, two mediating variables perceived benefits have positive relation with green accounting adoptions ($\beta = 0.19$, $t = 3.75$, $\text{sig} = 0.002$). Environmental concern positively creates an impact on green accounting adoption. ($\beta = 0.2638$, $t = 5.75$, $\text{sig} = 0.00$) supports H5. Here all five direct relations show positive effects and endogenous variables. This study also contributes to the effect size, individual predictive ability of exogenous variables. These results suggest that environmental knowledge has very strong predictive ability on perceived benefit while medium level predictive ability of environment knowledge on green accounting adoption and environmental concern to green accounting adoption.

(Cohen, J. , 1992). Overall structural model results suggest that all three exogenous variables explain 38.04% variance. The variables environmental knowledge, perceived benefits and environmental concern contributes 38.24 % in the incremental discussion of green accounting adoptions. Goodness of fit is the most vital aspect of the structural model. The estimated model of study indicates the values of SRMR - 0.0367, dULS = 2.79 and dG = 4.13. These values are less than 95% and 99% quartiles of the values. The above results suggested that the structural model is better and the goodness of fit index and further can be replicated or generalized for further analysis.

Effect	β	t	Significance	Decision
EKW \rightarrow PB \rightarrow GAD	0.1923	5.48	0.000	Support
EKW \rightarrow ENC \rightarrow GAD	0.0690	3.12	0.003	Support

Mediating/Indirect effect:

The study aims to mediate the effects of environmental concerns and perceived benefits on green accounting adoptions. According to recommendations (Jose, P. E., 2013) 5000 bootstrapping performed. ADANCO analysis suggested mediating (indirect) effect of environmental knowledge to perceived benefits to green accounting adoption. ($\beta = 0.1923$, $t = 5.48$, $\text{sig} = 0.00$). This positive significant influence clearly suggests that perceived benefit creates a higher level of Mediating effects than environmental knowledge - environmental concerns - green accounting adoption. ($\beta = 0.0690$, $t = 3.12$, $\text{sig} = 0.001$). The mediating effect clearly supports H6 and H7 in this structural model. Here in both the mediation cases partial mediation was established. As per the recommendations of (hair et al, 2014) VAF (Variance Accounted For) both mediating variables perceived benefits and environmental knowledge concern values were 0.5617 and 0.2018 respectively. These both values lie between $0.20 < \text{VAF} < 0.80$ suggests partial mediation. In this study both the mediation positively significantly contributes in structural models.

POLICY IMPLICATION -CONCLUSION

The result of the study Revealed Valuable inputs for researcher, marketers and Business leaders of emerging economies. These Business leaders are Keen to promote or adopt green accounting. The existing study findings provide empirical evidence for business leaders for adoption of green accounting. The results of this study confirm that environmental knowledge, perceived benefit and environmental concern have a positive impact on green accounting adoption. The study also confirmed positive Mediating effects of environmental concern and perceived benefit on green accounting adoption with respect to environmental knowledge. When business leaders incline to acquire environmental knowledge or showing their concern regarding environmental issues there adoption of green accounting gradually increases. Gujarat is land of entrepreneur, the business leaders of this States are known for calculative decision. These business leaders are always concerned regarding operational cost, sustainability and most importantly the accumulated profit in organizations. This study's

findings confirm the important role of perceived benefit in adoption of green accounting. These studies results were in line with (Newton, J. D., Tsarenko, Y., Ferraro, C., & Sands, S., 2015). Environmental concern play key role in the adoption of green accounting in developing economy. Study confirms the mediating effect of environmental concern and worksheet benefit on adoption of green accounting. The majority of the researchers exhibit European culture. While this study contributes to important factors like environmental knowledge. This study also confirms the results line with (Bhatt, V., 2021) higher the benefits will lead any consumer to adopt or buy any technological products. Findings of this study confirm that environmental concern and perceived benefit both mediating variables play a partial mediating role in this structural model. In addition to that, this model can be easily adopted in developing states like Gujarat and emerging economies like India.

At the outset, the study provides useful insights, how environmental knowledge, environmental concern and percent benefit create a positive significant impact on adoption or purchase of green accounting in micro small medium enterprises. Marketers of this product can understand the aspects of adoption of green accounting and various products related to environmental accounting, top marketer can formulate marketing strategies of such products. Which study will help marketer to design communication, prepare sales design techniques and construct sales promotion policies. In addition to that marketers can repair their discounts, sales promotion model most importantly payment method based on this study. (Williams, E., 2015). This study also provides valuable concern regarding sustainability, and increases the intention towards the green products. The manager can use eco-friendly products and environmental concerns to increase the trust and reduce the doubt regarding green technological products. Marketers should position the products by providing exhaustive information regarding environmental claim, make 1 users aware regarding future environmental challenges and provisional remedies. Finally manager Suit designed entire green products in such a manner that business leaders were inspired to adopt green accounting concerts.

Policy maker must understand the role of green accounting, not only to protect the environment but to play a crucial role in sustainable developments of any organization. The green accounting concepts more play meaningful role in any organization like effectiveness of various organization financial activity, optimum output of overall resources, controlling the unwanted expenditure, cost effectiveness and most importantly leads any organization leading towards profitability. This study will help any business leaders to help prepare, formulate, implement and monitor above activities in the organizations. The adoption of green accounting inclined business leaders to formulate or apply strategies will give benefit to all stakeholders of the company. The adoption policy will help any business leaders to achieve financial motive, social motive, and achievement of sense of responsibility. In the current development of adoption of green accounting policy makers play very vital role, the Gujarat government and central government create efforts regarding awareness of products, provide financial assistance to buy products related to organic, green or create renewable energy. Governments provide motivation to business leaders by providing subsidies to green products, giving tax benefits to business leaders and repurchasing the additional units produced by individuals. Policy maker can even makes changes in new renewable policy and invite business leaders to invest money in such companies that leads to sustainable growth.

Government forms certain laws related to environment protection and motivate business leaders to purchase green products. Policy makers can think about additional subsidies and adopt green technological products at zero money, entire money will be deducted from tax and small installments will help business leaders to purchase green products. Policy makers should give awards to top business leaders who implement the operations of green accounting most successfully. Policy makers must create awareness regarding the benefits of adopting green accounting in terms of reduced cost, financial effectiveness, operational efficiency and profitability which gradually leads to sustainability. The above discussion clearly suggests that inspiring beneficial policies and education regarding technology and green products motivate business leaders to adopt or increase purchase intention of green accounting products. The above policy makers' initiatives may reduce doubt, increase trust, and may lead to adopt green accounting products and create sustainable organizations.

Limitations:

Future research can be developed with various behavioral and social factors of business leaders of adoption of green accounting. This study focuses on only positive influence of various environmental and core variables like perceived benefit, however negative variables organizational challenges or technical hazards or higher adoption cost was ignored in this study. This research focuses only on the adoption of green accounting, post implementation challenges like operational barrier or variable cost are ignored in the study, so far as demographic limitations, and this study aims for green accounting adoption in one of the fastest developing states in GUJARAT. This study can be replicated in other states of India or any other emerging country. In future researcher can apply some other theories or extended model with some additional variables and model can replicate in other areas. Overall this is one of the valuable contributions in the area of adoption of green accounting in emerging economies.

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